

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF HERBAL SUNSCREEN**Shital N. Magar***

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ABSTRACT

The formulation and evaluation of herbal sunscreen using orange, liquid paraffin, lavender oil, tomato juice, corn starch, aloe vera, honey and green aims to create a natural sunscreen product that harnesses the potential sun protection properties of these herbal ingredients. This study explores the combination of these ingredients to develop a sunscreen formulation that provides effective protection against harmful ultraviolet (UV) radiation. The formulation process involves determining the appropriate proportions of each ingredient to achieve the desired consistency and sun protection factor (SPF) of the sunscreen. Orange extract or juice is chosen for its antioxidant properties, while liquid paraffin serves as an emollient and moisturizing agent. Lavender oil is included for its soothing properties and pleasant fragrance. Tomato juice, rich in

lycopene, is selected for its potential UV absorbing properties. Corn starch acts as a thickening agent to enhance structure. Aloe Vera gel offers moisturization and cooling effect. Honey contributes to hydration and antibacterial properties, while green tea extract provides additional antioxidant benefit. The evaluation of herbal sunscreen involves several steps. Sensory evaluation assesses the texture, fragrance and overall user experience of the sunscreen. Stability testing is performed to monitor any changes in color, consistency, odor, or efficacy over time.

KEYWORDS: -Skin, SPF, Sun protection, Antioxidant, Moisturizing, Consistency.

INTRODUCTION

From the dawn of mankind, Sun is source of life and energy. But recent studies accept sun as main offender of harmful effects including acute effects (e.g., sunburn and drug-induced photo toxicity) and chronic risks of frequent sun ray exposure like sunburn, crack, malignance and pigmentation, cancer and immune suppression.^[1] Skin melanoma, sunburn, photoaging, skin pigmentation, and various painful or hazardous effects are caused by UVA and UVB rays.^[7] UV protection is becoming very popular because of sunscreen's properties as a photo-protecting agent.^[4] The use of sunscreen is a necessity these days to protect our skin from the severe ultraviolet (UV) rays. It is tough to find good sun protection formulation which is non-greasy and moisturizing to the skin. The herbal sunscreen will not only protect the skin from the effects of harmful UV rays but also remove the use of chemical sunscreens.^[5] Sunscreen preparations are designed to be used topically to avoid UV radiation from entering the skin directly by absorbing or reflecting from the skin.^[9] Sunscreen preparation is applied topically, and its persistence is to heal, prevent or resist skin from painful or harmful effects of sunburn, suntan, sun cancer, and premature skin aging and to intensify the level of Sun Protection Factor (SPF).^[6] Sunscreen products can be formulated in the form of lotions, creams, sticks, aerosols, gels, powders and ointments.^[8] Herbal ingredients such as green tea, amla, lemon, turmeric etc. have shown properties such as absorbance of a broad spectrum of UV rays, antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects. They also cause skin tightening, help prevent skin damage, heal acne, disappear scars, lighten dark circles and effectively make skin glowing. These herbal products also provide self-color so the use of artificial colors may be avoided.^[8]

• Advantages of herbal sunscreen

1. Easily available.
2. Do not provide allergy
3. Easy to manufacture.
4. Cheap in cost.
5. Effective with small quantity.

AIM

To Formulate and Evaluate Herbal Sunscreen by using orange and Aloe vera extract.

OBJECTIVE

- To lowering the risk of skin cancer with the help of herbs.
- They play an important role in blocking ultraviolet (UV) radiation from being absorbed by the skin.
- It can tolerate heat, light and sweat, not readily absorb into the skin, not create any toxic reactions to the skin.
- Herbal sunscreen is providing antioxidants, and nourishing oils, providing hydration and skin benefits.
- Consistent use of sunscreen can minimize the visible signs of aging and promote smoother, more radiant complexion overtime.

MATERIALS AND METHODS COLLECTION OF MATERIALS

1. MATERIALS

1. Orange Extract Or Fresh Oranges

Synonyms: Apricot, salmon

Orange peel, the zesty outer skin of oranges is rich in taste and nutrients. The peel has two main layers: the flavedo (outer colorful layer) and the albedo (interior white, spongy layer). Oranges are citrus fruits that grow on evergreen trees and are cultivated in subtropical and tropical climates around the world. Orange peel's exfoliating and brightening characteristics make it suitable for use in skincare treatments. It can be crushed into a powder and used with other substances to create face masks or scrub. It has antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties.^[11]

Kingdom: Plantae

Division: Magnoliophyta

Class: Magnoliopsida

Order: sapindales

Family: Rutuaceae

Genus: Citrus Sinensis

Species: sweet Orange

Fig: 1.1 Orange Fruit.

2. Liquid Paraffin (Mineral Oil)

Paraffin oil, also known as liquid paraffin, is extremely valued for its hydrating and protective properties. It works by forming a protective barrier on the skin's surface, which helps to trap moisture and prevent it from evaporating. This makes paraffin oil particularly beneficial for individuals with dry skin, as it helps to keep the skin hydrated and protected from environmental.^[12]

3. Lavender Oil

Synonyms: Lavandula, French Lavender

Reduces skin inflammation and enhances wound healing. Lavender Oil is obtained from flowers of the lavender plant. It is widely used in skincare and aromatherapy products for its calming and soothing properties. Lavender oil has a pleasant fragrance and is often included in products like lotions, creams, soaps, or bath products. It may also have antiseptic or anti-inflammatory effects on the skin.^[13]

Kingdom: Plantae

Class: Magnoliopsida

Order: Lamiales

Family: Lamiaceae

Genus: Lavandula L

Species: Lavandula Angustifolia

Fig: 1.2 Lavender Oil.

4. Tomato Juice

Synonyms: Lycopersicon Esculentum

The extract is derived by crushing tomatoes to produce crude tomato juice, which is then separated into serum and pulp. Tomato juice is the liquid extracted from tomatoes. It is rich in antioxidants, including lycopene, which has potential benefits for the skin.

In skincare formulations, tomato juice is sometimes use for its brightening properties or to reduce the appearance of pores. It can be added to cleansers, toners, or masks.^[14]

Kingdom: Plant

Division: Angiosperms

Class: Magnoliopsida

Order; Seaplant

Family: Solanaceae

Genus: Solanum

Species: Solanum Lycopersicum

Fig: 1.3 Tomato Juice.

5. Corn Starch

- Corn starch is a fine white powder derived from corn. It is commonly used as a thickening agent in skincare and cosmetics products.
- In formulations like creams, lotions, or powders, corn starch helps provide texture and stability. It gives products a smoother consistency and can also help absorb excess moisture.

Fig: 1.4 Corn Starch.

6. Aloe Vera gel

Synonym: Aloe Barbadensis Mill

Aloe is naturally rich in Vitamin A, C, E, B12, antioxidants, phytosterols, polysaccharides, folic acid, etc. Aloe Vera is extensively used in cosmetics and beauty products for all good reasons. It has become anti-viral and antibacterial properties, and the ability to treat your skin effectively.^[10]

Kingdom: Plantae

Division: Magnoliophyta

Class; Liliopsida

Order: Asparagales

Family: Asphodelaceae

Genus: Aloe L

Fig: 1.5 Aloe Vera.

7. Honey

- Synonyms: Mudhu.

Honey is a great natural ingredient for moisturizers due to its humectant and antibacterial properties. It draws moisture from the air and into the skin, keeping it hydrated and soft. Additionally, honey's antibacterial qualities can help with acne and promote a clearer appearance.^[15]

Biological Source: Apise Mellifera

Family: Apidae

Fig: 1.6 Honey

8. Green tea extract or green tea leaves

- Synonyms: Jenmaichan

Many scientists believe that free radicals contribute to the aging process as well as the development of a number of health problems. Polyphenols present in green tea helps in antiaging. Makes your skin looks younger and better and give even skin tone.^[16]

Kingdom: Plante

Family: Theaceae

Class: Dillenidea

Order: Theales

Genus: Camelia L

Species: Camellia Sinensis

Fig: 1.7 Green Tea.

FORMULATION

Table No.1.1

Sr. No	Ingredients	Quantity	Use
1	Orange	40%	Antioxidant
2	Liquid paraffin	5%	Emollient
3	Lavender oil	1%	Fragrance and Soothing Property
4	Tomato juice	10%	Reduce appearance of pores and Brightening property
5	Corn starch	3.5%	Thickening Agent
6	Aloe Vera	30%	Moisturizing and Healing agent
7	Honey	5%	Antibacterial
8	Green tea	3.5	antioxidant
9	Borax	0.5%	Cleanser
10	Steric Acid	3.5%	Emollient

METHODS

1. O/W Emulsion
2. W/O Emulsion

1. O/W Emulsion

Emulsion oil in water [O/W] is composed of an oil phase dispersed in an aqueous one known as a direct emulsion. Stabilization of O/W emulsion is often performed with hydrophilic-hydrophobic particles. It is nongreasy and easily removable from the skin.

2. W/O Emulsion

Water as the dispersed phase and oil as dispersion medium. Greasy and not water washable. Used externally to prevent. Evaporation of moisture from the surface of skin e.g. cold cream. Preferred for external use like creams.^[8]

We have chosen O/W methods to make herbal sunscreen.

1. O/W Emulsion

Procedure

- a. Determine the desired proportions of each ingredient based on the desired consistency and SPF of the sunscreen.
- b. Prepare the orange extract by squeezing fresh oranges or using commercially available orange extract.
- c. Aloe Vera gel and tomato juice is mixed well, and form aqueous phase.
- d. Steric acid, liquid paraffin, borax are melt and form oil phase.
- e. Above both phases are mixed well with continuous stirring and add orange extract with excipients like lavender oil, green tea.
- f. Store in closed tight container.^[3]

EVALUATION OF FORMULATION

1. Phytochemical investigation: Phytochemical screening is very important parameter to determine the Phytoconstituents in the extract. Phytochemical study of Orange Extract.
2. Physical Evaluation: For test formulation was observed for color odor texture and test.
3. Viscosity: Viscosity of formulation was done by using Brookfield viscometer at room temperature of 280C using spindle no.6 at 20 RPM.
4. PH: The pH meter was calibrated by using a standard buffer solution. About 0.5 of the herbal sunscreen cream was weighed and dissolved in 50.0ml of distilled water and its pH was measured by digital pH meter.
5. Skin Irritation Test: Area of one cm² marked on left hand dorsal surface. Then emulsion was applied to that area & noted for 24 hours. Then it is checked for irritancy, erythema & reported.
6. Greasiness test: Here the emulsion was applied on the skin surface in the form of smear and checked if the smear was oily or grease like.
7. Washability: A small amount of emulsion was applied on hand and then washed with tap water.

8. SPF: Sun protection factor is a metric for determining how effective a sunscreen product is. In this work, the sunscreen activity of a cream formulation containing Orange Extract was assessed using an in-vitro SPF technique.^[2,3]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Formulations of various concentrations are prepared and evaluated, and the result is follows

- **Phytochemical Investigation**

Table No.1.2

Sr.No	Test Name	Procedure	Result
1	Test for Tannins: Gelatin Test	orange extract is dissolved in 5ml. distilled water + 1% gelatin solution 10% NaCl	A white precipitate
2	Test for Flavonoids : Alkaline reagent test	orange Extract + 10% ammonium hydroxide sol	A Yellow Fluorescence
3	Test for Terpenoids	2ml chloroform+5ml. orange extract, (evaporated on water bath) 3ml. conc. H ₂ SO ₄ (boiled on water bath)	A grey colored solution

1. Physical evaluation

Herbal sunscreen formulation was white coloured which was having sweet odour, semisolid and smooth texture.^[17]

2. Viscosity

The Brookfield viscometer was used to measure the viscosity, with the proper number of spindles selected. 50 ml beaker was used to hold 20 g of preparation until the spindles groove was dipped and the rpm was set. Herbal sunscreen viscosity was measured at 5,10,20,50 and 100 rpm Viscosity of sunscreen formulation was found to be 4332.^[22]

3. PH

The pH of herbal sunscreen was determined by using digital pH meter. pH was measured after 0.5 g of formulation was dissolved in 50 ml of newly prepared distilled water for 2 hours. The pH of the formulated herbal sunscreen was similar to the pH of the skin after 24 hours of use i.e. 6.8.^[18]

4. Skin irritation test

The herbal sunscreen cream was applied on the skin and observed for 24 hours, as an outcome it shows no signs of any irritation, redness, itching or swelling on the skin.^[20]

5. Greasiness test

The sunscreen cream was non-greasy shown by greasiness test.

6. Washability

Small amount of herbal sunscreen cream was applied to the glass slide and then washed with tap water to conduct the wash ability test. The observation was easily washable.^[21]

7. SPF

A UV spectrophotometer was used to study the in- vitro efficiency of herbal sunscreen.

SPF was calculated using the equation below. Three times each sample was considered.

$$\text{SPF} = \text{CF} \sum \text{EE}(\lambda) \times \text{I}(\lambda) \times \text{A}(\lambda)$$

Where as, CF= correction factor; EE= Erythemogenic effect; I= Intensity of solar light of wavelength; A= Absorbance.^[19]

CONCLUSION

The Study Attempted to develop herbal sunscreen cream using orange extract and examine their efficacy for preventing sun burn. Herbal sunscreen offers several advantages over chemical sunscreen. It is made from natural ingredients, reducing the risk of skin irritation and allergic reactions. Herbal sunscreens are also safer for the environment, as they do not contain harmful chemicals that can harm marine life and coral reefs. They often provide broad- spectrum protection and may have antioxidant properties, further protecting the skin from sun damage. However, it is important to choose an herbal sunscreen with appropriate SPF and test it on a small patch of skin before applying it to the entire body. In the pursuit of natural and environmentally-friendly skincare solutions, the development of herbal sunscreens derived from orange peel extract has garnered significant attention. The use of topical herbal remedies and cosmetics has become increasingly popular among consumers, driven by the perception that botanical compounds are safer and healthier than their synthetic counterparts. Recent studies have highlighted the potential of naturally-derived UV absorbers, such as vitamins, polyphenols, carotenoids, and amino acids, as viable alternatives to conventional chemical UV absorbers, which have been criticized for their adverse human and environmental health impacts.

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